

8T – Curvature Spikes

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Abstract:

By analyzing the main equation of the 8T, a varying a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature it is possible to understand the relationship among families in rather simple and elegant way. The high mass family (T-B) is a high curvature spike, overtime such spike decompose to lower spikes, i.e. lower mass families. The opposite can occur at very high energy.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $M = M_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the matric tensor, given by the conditions on (1.1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is wrapped in an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvature and so flatten each other, given by equations (1.2) and (1.21).

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0, \quad -\frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial S_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial S_n} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial S_1} \frac{\partial S_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial S_n} \frac{\partial S_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.21)$$

;

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (2)$$

We have proven the term to vanish into fermions by showing it has two elements that differ in sign and appear in an even number. However, it does not provide us to which family it decompose. Since it was proven that there is a decreasing series of families, starting from (T-B), which is the first, going to (U-D) which is the third, we can predict that the curvature spikes get weaker and lower over time. We can make three predictions regarding curvature spikes converging inward:

- (1) The colder the manifold the smaller the ratio between low spikes to higher spikes. U-D is more common than T-B on the matric tensor than T-B.
- (2) At early stage of the universe T-B was more common than the second and third families.
- (3) The colder the universe, the lower spikes of aspiring zero mass families will be observed. Dark matter effect is increasing adiabatically, it should grow with time.

The relation between family formation and temperature is simple. Assuming at the flattening moment the temperature was immensely high, the arbitrary curvature converging were high as well, first in order. Nature than starts eliminating by devising in increasing amounts, as time goes by the universe gets colder than lower curvature spikes converging appearing more common on the matric tensor. High spikes decay into lower spikes, from T-B we reach U-D.

Such a construction is supported by the Quark mass series, given by equation (3) or (3.1). Since nature can not truly eliminate the arbitrary variations due to the numerator being $mod(2) \neq 0$ the result is an endless succession of families below first generation. The visualization above is only a small segment. N_E is to a function for two multiple of variations and next family total mass predicted 0.113 Mev.

$$M_{N+1} = \frac{M_N + (7)}{7 * \prod_{E=1}^r N_E} * \frac{1}{9}; \quad (3)$$

$$M_{N+1} = \frac{M_N + (7)}{7 * \prod_{E=1}^r N_E} \quad (3.1)$$

$$N_E = 2E ; E \geq 1$$

References

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